

THE RELATIONSHIP OF SELF-EFFICACY WITH TEHRAN CITY HIGH SCHOOL STUDENT'S MOTIVATION AND TAKING PART IN PHYSICAL ACTIVITIES

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Abstract:

The present study has investigated the relationship of self-efficacy with Tehran city high school student's motivation and taking part in physical activities. The present study methodologically is divided in to 8 kind's hypothesis inductive research approaches, quantitative research strategy, the objectives of the research are descriptive and explaining, and in the end of method and data collection, library resources review and questionnaire. The statistical society of this research consists of all the students of Tehran education districts 14, 6, 3 in 2013 – 2014 academic years. To specify the sample volume Cochran formula was used. Based on this formula the minimum needed volume for this sample for such a research are 203 individuals. The research sample consisted in 400 of Tehran education students (boys and girls) that were selected via stratified cluster sampling method among girls and boys students. The data collection tool was a standard questionnaire. To analyses the research findings, Pearson correlation coefficient and multi-variable regression model in %95 coefficient level were used. The result showed that in the research statistical sample, the subjects have evaluated self-efficacy characteristics higher than average, and evaluated important individuals subscales lower than average. And also specified that there isn't significant relation between self-efficacy and physical activities and motivation to participate in sports, with %95 confidence level. And also calculated coefficient of determination showed that %2.56 of physical activities variance and %3.68 of motivation to participate in sports is specified via self-efficacy.

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1. Introduction

Self-efficacy is an individual's belief and trust to his abilities, in a specific behavior, to the intended result (Bandura, 1997). Bandura declares that self-efficacy is an effective capacity that human cognitive, social, emotional and behavioral skills are organized in an effective way to different aims realization (Shoars, 2014). In relation to self-efficacy studies it should be said that self-efficacy beliefs ends to more motivation in work environment and learning better management styles to have efficient relationship with the students (Cryon & Jacob 2013). In many cases, teachers chart academic year with a high motivation, but in different reason these motivations have been turned off and they face inability, lack of self and situation satisfaction that mostly are because of low self-efficacy beliefs against class subjects (Vencore & Kendal, 2006).

Many researchers studied student's motivation and participation in physical activities. They introduced the most important motivations between the students: learning new skill, improving sport current skills, enjoying physical readiness, enjoying healthy competitions and earning reputation and positions. Yosof (2011) believe that the student's motivation to attend in school physical education classes is individual growth, social interaction and environmental adaptation, that we can take steps by increasing internal and external motivations among students and creating special favorites and attractiveness in student's attraction for physical education activities and sports. Milis et al (2007) studies internal motivation in different age groups. The study results showed that by rise in age, internal motivation, to attend in sport activities, increases. It seems that by increasing age, the individuals evaluate their participation in sport and entertainment, enjoyment and amusement, and they pay less attention to external motivation.

Participation in physical activities and sports are important factors to prevent obesity and its consequences. Based on studies obesity prevalence among the Iranian youth is higher than defined standards by prevention and control centers and these rates are higher among girls. So teenager and youth girl's participation in physical and sport activities and awareness of their motivations are important issues in health expansion among this group, and there are many studies about it (Gaw et al, 2008).

For instance, Pero et al (2009) did a study to the aim of investigating the effect of age, competitive level and sex, on the athletes sport motivation. The results of this study showed that the age and competitive level interaction (Local, provincial, national and international) on total motivation index and also on external motivation is significant. And also Stephan, Boron et al (2009) investigated elderly women predictor motivation in

participation or leave - physical activities. The results of this study showed that the individuals who left physical activities had a low level autonomy motivation, while their lack of motivation was in a high level. The results of cluster analysis showed that there are 3 motivational profiles between those who continued sport cooperation and participation:

- 1) High composition, high scores autonomy motivation and inner projection and average scores in external set;
- 2) high inner projection average scores in autonomy motivation, high score in setting inner projection and low scores in out setting; and
- 3) average inner projection low scores in autonomy motivation. Average scores in setting inner projection and low scores in external setting.

The results of this study showed that the women participate in physical activity may have different motivational profile. Generally the effective factors for general sports participation are gaining vitality, enjoyment, touch sport benefits and its positive effects, immunity against illness, lack of serious danger in general and public sports, discharging and disposal of toxins, gain social emotions, group dependency, physical illness treatment, low cast, lack of need to special equipment's and finally escape from life problems, and forget them. So in this research the relationship of self-efficacy with motivation and participating in physical activities of elementary school students are investigated.

2. Research methodology

The present research psychologically is divided in to 8 layers of paradigm viewpoints, The original type of practical research, deductive research approaches, hypothesis, quantitative research strategies, field research field, survey and critical research methods, purpose of the research description and explanation, and finally data collection methods, review the library resources and questionnaires.

The statistical society of this research is consisted all Tehran education students of 3, 6 and 14 restricts of 2013- 2014 years. Cochran formula is used to specify the sample volume. Based on this formula the minimum sample volume needed for such a research is 203 individuals. The research sample consists in 400 students of Tehran education that were selected among male and female students. In this research data, collection tool was a standard questionnaire and were adjusted in 3 parts, and in the following order, as a general questionnaire, were available for the subjects:

A. Self-efficacy scale

Consisted 17 questions that covered 3 subscales (willing to behavioral intuition), effort continuation to complete the behavior and resistance against facing obstacles). Mentioned questionnaire questions were extracted from standard Sherer et al (1982) questionnaire.

The measuring scale of this questionnaire was Likert type and 1 to 5 points were allocated to each answer. The highest point for self-efficacy was 85 and the lowest 17. The highest points indicated higher and stronger self-efficacy. Sherer (1982) mentioned calculated validity %76 via Cronbach's alpha for general self-efficiency. And also fir structural validity, calculated correlation with Rutter inhibition (1966) and Baron's endurance (1953).

B) Motivation scale to participate in sports activities (PMQ)

Consisted 30 questions that seven subscales (reputation, internal motivation, discharging energy, belonging to friends, group ability, willingness to excitement, and important people) from mentioned questionnaire were extracted from Gale, Hodlston, Gross (1983). This questionnaire measuring scale was Likert and each answer consisted 1 to 5 points. The highest point of sport cooperation motivation was 150, and the lowest point was 30. The highest points show higher and stronger co- operation.

C. Physical activity scale

Physical activity scale consisted 4 questions for evaluating duration of workout, number of sessions in a week and training intensity. The minimum point of this questionnaire is 4 and maximum point was 20, and medium or average point for individual's segmentation criterion in two active and inactive groups. In the way that the individuals got points higher than average are active in the group and those got points lower than average are inactive in the group. In the end the researcher for data collection, by referring to Tehran ministry of education and present thesis subject and test samples and utilized questionnaire in the research, Proceeded by obtaining a license.

After obtaining license to in- person presence at schools and questionnaire delivery made the necessary coordination with some school headmasters. To justify selected individuals in sampling, a summary of research objective and the important of their honesty in answering the questionnaire questions were described and finally the questionnaires were delivered and collected. To analyse the research findings, Pearson coefficient correlation and multi-purpose regression model in %95 confidence level is used.

3. Findings

Based on the following table values, the highest point average is related to self-efficacy (47.15) and the lowest point average was related to the important people subscale (10.92). This result showed that in statistical of the research, the subjects (triangles) evaluated the self-efficacy characteristics higher than average and individuals subscales of important people lower than average.

Table 1: The main variables and its subscales description using descriptive indicators

Variable	$\bar{X}$	Sd
Physical activity	11.12	4.38
Self-efficacy	47.15	9.28
Popularity	21.80	5.73
Inner motivation	22.90	5.69
Internal drain	15.45	3.40
Belonging to a friend	11.98	2.52
Accepting group	11.45	3.20
Thrill-seeking	19.15	4.20
Important people	10.92	3.22

In the following statistical analysis of the results of statistical sample is generalized to statistical society. Due to Pearson's test results the significance level resulted between self-efficacy variables with physical activities and sports cooperation or participation is more than determined Alpha. So the zero theory is admitted and the other one is rejected, it means that by %95 confidence level it can be said that there isn't a significant relation between self-efficacy with physical activity and the motivation of sports participation. And also calculated coefficient showed that %2.56 of physical variances and % 3.68 of sports motivation participation variance is determined through self- efficacy.

Table 2: Dependent and independent variables estimation

Var	Physical Activity	Motivation Of Sports Participation
Self-efficacy	.160	-.192
P-Value	.325	.235
R square	2.56%	3.68%
**Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed)		
*Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed)		

4. Discussion and conclusion

Sports from the ancient time have been a fact for human in human societies and had been a part of their daily life. One of the most important challenges human faces in present societies is the lack of movement prevalence culture and indolence among people. Industrialization of societies and entering different technological world has affected human life dimensions including his movement. Regular physical activities cause mental and physical health and have positive and effective results. The inner desire of human to the physical activities is something inherent. In primitive societies or in ancient culture there weren't organized physical education plans, but physical activities were inseparable

components of daily life, and healthy, strong and trained bodies were apparent characteristics of people their time. So social relationships, physical education, and sports have mutual effects on each other, and are effective in providing mental health, thinking style, self-confidence, character genesis and socialization. In this research the relationships of self-efficacy with physical activity and sports participation motivation is investigated.

The results showed that there isn't a significant relation between student's self-efficacy and physical activities index. Studies and researches can refer to: sex, age, the history of sports championship. For example, past findings show that there is a significant difference between girls and boys high school students in sport activities participation. And also in the following it was determined that there isn't a significant relation between the students self-efficacy and attending sports activities motivation.

The result of this research isn't in line with past findings. Given that self-efficacy is constructed inner motivation level components, this factor can be the reason for inconsistency of present research results with other researches. Bahram & Shafizadeh (2015) in investigating the relationships of goal orientation and perceived ability with motivation of attending Junior school students and high school students of Tehran city, in physical activities, reported the inner motivation level the most important motivations for students participation.

Due to the essence of different academic periods of students, it can be said that junior school students mostly by exterior motives and high school students mostly by interior motives, direct their sports behavior.

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